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ASSOCIATION OF CANOPY SPECTRAL REFLECTANCE INDICES AND YIELD COMPONENTS OF WINTER WHEAT (*TRITICUM AESTIVUM* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Grain yield of wheat is a complex trait made up of the interaction between different yield components and environmental effects. Due to the importance of yield traits, breeders need efficient and precise methods to measure differences among genotypes. Since that spectral proximal sensing is promising for high-throughput non-destructive phenotyping, recent findings suggest that multispectral proximal sensors can be used in place of labour intensive methods to estimate specific plant traits. The objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of different spectral reflectance indices (SRIs) in assessing stem height and spike length in 4 winter wheat genotypes grown in different conditions of seed priming. Seeds of each winter wheat genotypes were primed with different concentrations of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) and after sown in soil pots. Spectral reflectance from the plants at different growth stages during vegetation was measured using an active multispectral, optical sensor namely Plant-O-Meter. Since that device provides four indicative wavelengths between 465, 535, 630 and 850 nm, several SRIs were calculated. The results revealed that most of SRIs measured at full flowering stage (BBCH 65) of wheat were positively correlated ($P < 0.01$) with stem height of wheat, with r values of up to 0.674. For the trait spike length of wheat the greatest positive association was found at medium milk grown stage (BBCH 75) of wheat under each treatment, with r values of up to 0.798. Overall, statistically significant correlations were more influenced by the phenological stage of estimation and the index used.

Keywords: *Wheat, Spectral vegetation indices, yield traits.*

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is one of the world's most important staple crops and provides 20% of the food calories and similar proportion of daily protein to the world's population (Reynolds and Braun, 2013). Obtaining wheat cultivars with high genetic potential for grain yield, as well as good quality of wheat are the main priority of breeding programs (Petrović et al., 2012). The grain yield of wheat is a complex trait that depends on mainly yield components and environmental factors (Kraljević-Balalić et al., 1995; Zečević et al., 2008). The knowledge of association between grain yield and its components can improve the efficiency of breeding programs by identifying appropriate traits for selecting wheat varieties (Evans and Fisher, 1999; Zečević et al., 2008). Stem height and spike length are important quantitative trait which are in correlations with other yield components. It has been confirmed that nanotechnology poses great potential to increase

plant growth and different grain yield traits. Seed priming with zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) has been shown as prominent to enhance yield components, such as plant height and spike length in wheat (Munir et al., 2018; Rizwan et al., 2019, Ljubičić et al., 2020). On the other side, its sufficient concentration could raise negative effects and decrease growth. However, due to the importance of yield traits, breeders need efficient and precise methods to measure differences among genotypes. Recent findings suggest that multispectral proximal sensors can be used in place of labour intensive methods to estimate specific plant traits. The spectral signatures reflected from the plant canopy at specific wavelengths provide different types of cumulative information on the substantial and gradual changes that occur in specific plant characteristics or tolerance levels (El-Hendawy et al., 2019). Crop spectral reflectance measurements are being used efficiently for crop growth monitoring as they reflect wide range of biochemical and physiological measures, while spectral reflectance indices (SRIs) are quantitative measurement and present a spectral transformation metric for measuring the presence and state of vegetation (Bannari et al., 1995). Spectral reflectance indices (SRIs) have been developed on the basis of simple mathematical formulae such as ratios or differences in reflectance at given wavelengths Araus et al. (2001). Its basis is the characteristic photosynthetic response of green vegetation to incident light (Khan et al., 2018). Attempts have been made to evaluate the potential use of SRIs in breeding to differentiate genotypes for yield under different conditions (Aparacio et al. 2001; Royo et al. 2003; Babar et al. 2006; Babar et al. 2007). Several studies have dealt with different SRIs as indirect selection traits and their potential as an indirect selection tool has been evaluated based on the basis of its genetic correlation and heritability (Babar et al., 2006; Gutierrez et al., 2010; El-Hendawy et al., 2019). The most widespread application of these indices is in the assessment of characteristics related to the total photosynthetic area of the canopy (Aparacio et al., 2000). Among numerous SRIs, the most widely used are the Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), Green normalised difference vegetation index (NDVIg), simple ratio (SR) and Transformed difference vegetation index (TDVI). However, the accuracy is influenced by the climate, growth stage of evaluation and the index used (Bolton and Friedl 2013). Since that wheat seed priming with zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs) is the main constraint in this investigation, the object of this paper was to estimate the performance of different SRIs, during the second half of the crop cycle, in assessing changes in stem height and spike length of wheat genotypes primed with different concentration of ZnO NPs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at the experimental greenhouse facility available in the University of Novi Sad, in Serbia, during the 2018-2019 growing season. The experimental material in this study was comprised from 4 winter wheat genotypes, namely, Pobeda, NS 40S, Ingenio and Futura. Seeds of each wheat genotypes were primed with different solutions containing appropriate concentrations of ZnO NPs (0, 10, 100 and 1000 mg L⁻¹) for 48 h in dark box by continuous aeration. Primed seeds of wheat were after sown in soil pots filled with 5.0 kg of soil, with 60-70% moisture contents during the whole experiment. The trial was set up according to the completely randomized design with three replications of each treatment on chernozem soil. For each winter wheat genotypes within each treatment spectral reflectance was measured at three different growth stages: full flowering (BBCH 65), medium milk (BBCH 75) and fully ripe stage (BBCH 89). For spectral reflectance measurements, an active, multispectral, optical sensor Plant-O-Meter proximal sensor, recently developed in BioSens

Institute, was used. Plant-O-Meter is an active hand-held sensor, which emits light and measures the reflectance at four indicative wavelengths, 465 nm (Blue), 535 nm (Green), 630 nm (Red) and 850 nm (Infrared). The sensor records the reflectance for each band separately providing the ability to calculate more than 30 different indices. Detailed information concerning the work principles and specifications of the Plant-O-Meter multispectral device has been provided in Kitić et al. (2019). Spectral measurements were taken close to noon, between 10:00 am and 2:00 pm on sunny, cloud-free days when the plant canopy and soil surface are dry. Reflectance from the vegetation was measured at 3 growth stages of wheat: full flowering (BBCH 65), medium milk (BBCH 75) and full rippe stage of wheat (BBCH 89). Based on Blue (465 nm), Green (535 nm), Red (630 nm) and Infrared (850 nm) spectral wavebands the following spectral reflectance indices were calculated: Normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), Red normalised difference vegetation index (RDVI), Green normalised difference vegetation index (NDVIg), Blue normalised difference vegetation index (NDVIb), Simple ratio (SR), Modified simple ratio (MSR), Infrared Percentage Vegetation Index (IPVI), Structure Insensitive Pigment Index (SIPI), Green Atmospherically Resistant Index (GARI), Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Green Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (GSAVI), Green Optimized Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (GOSAVI), Normalized Pigment Chlorophyll Ratio Index (NPCl), Green Chlorophyll Index (GCI), Green Ratio Vegetation Index (GRVI), Plant Senescence Reflectance Index (PSRI), Non-Linear Index (NLI), Transformed Difference Vegetation Index (TDVI), Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index (VARI), Wide Dynamic Range Vegetation Index (WDRVI), Green Re-normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GRDVI), Green-Blue NDVI (GBNDVI), Red-Blue NDVI (RBNDVI), Pan NDVI (PNDVI), Inversion of the simple ratio (ISR), Normalised difference water index (NDWI), Green leaf index (GLI) and Triangular Greenness Index (TGI). Calculation and selection of spectral reflectance indices were according to the mathematical formulae described according to the *Index database for remote sensing indices* (<https://www.indexdatabase.de/info/idb.php>). At the stage of full maturity, ten plants from each replication of each treatment of wheat genotypes were selected for measuring data for stem height and spike length. Average values of three replication trait analysis were used. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to study the relationship between vegetation indices and plant height and spike length of wheat. All statistical analyses were carried out using software STATISTICA, version 13 (StatSoft Inc., USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Yield components performance.

The presented results revealed wide range between the minimum and maximum values for observed traits of wheat within each treatment. The stem height of each wheat genotype increased with increasing ZnO NPs concentration applied. The greatest increase in stem height was found at 100 mg L⁻¹ ZnO NPs for genotypes NS 40S (89.3 cm) and NK Ingenio (86 cm), while genotypes with greatest increase at 10 mg L⁻¹ ZnO NPs applied were NS Futura (89 cm) and NS Pobeda (86 cm). Lower values of plant height were observed at control plants, ranged between 73 cm to 80 cm. The lowest values of plant height were found in maximum concentration of ZnO NPs ranged between 61 cm to 69 cm (Table 1).

Table 1. The mean values of stem height and spike length of examined 4 winter wheat genotypes

Yield components								
Treatment s	Stem height (cm)				Spike length (cm)			
	Environments							
	K - 0 mg l ⁻¹	10 mg	100 mg l ⁻¹	1000	K - 0 mg l ⁻¹	10	100 mg l ⁻¹	1000
Genotypes	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}
Pobeda	79.7	86.0	85.0	67.3	9.3	9.9	9.8	8.7
NS40S	75.0	83.7	89.3	63.7	10.2	11.1	11.2	9.7
Ingenio	74.7	82.7	86.0	65.3	9.9	10.7	11.1	9.3
Futura	75.0	89.0	88.0	64.3	10.9	11.3	11.3	9.9
\bar{x}	76.1	85.3	87.1	65.2	10.1	10.8	10.8	9.4

\bar{x} - mean value (cm); *Environment labels represents control (0), 10, 100 and 1000 mg l⁻¹ primed concentrations of ZnO NPs applied.

The present results indicated that different treatments influenced on differences in stem height which was expected since that the stem height is a quantitative and variable trait which expression highly depends on the environmental factors. With respect to the trait spike length the results indicated that spike length increase with increasing ZnO NPs concentrations in the priming solution, comparing than control conditions. The highest increase in spike length was found in conditions of 10 mg l⁻¹ and 100 mg l⁻¹ NPs ZnO applied, while the lower values of spike length were found in cultivars in control conditions. The greatest increase in spike length within application of 10 mg l⁻¹ ZnO NPs were observed for genotypes Futura (11.3 cm) and Pobeda (9.9 cm). Wheat cultivars with greatest increase at 100 mg l⁻¹ ZnONPs applied were NS 40S (9.8 cm) and NK Ingenio (11.1 cm). Lower values of spike length were observed at plants in control conditions which values ranged between 9.3 cm to 10.9 cm. In conditions of maximum concentration of ZnO NPs applied the lowest values of these parameters were found (Table 1). The present results indicated that different treatments influenced the differences in spike length. According to Zečević et al. (2008), spike length is genetically controlled, but it highly depends to environmental factors. In general, results showed that ZnO NPs increased the plant growth and confirmed that ZnO NPs are effective in increasing plant growth and stem height. These results are in accordance with results published by Munir et al. (2018) and Rizwan et al. (2019).

Effect of environment on yield components and spectral reflectance indices (SRIs).

The presented results revealed wide range between the minimum and maximum values for spectral reflectance indices (SRIs), as well as for individual spectral bands for green vegetation detection which varied on overall basis. Regarding to the overall mean values, the maximum

values most of SRIs were observed during full flowering stage (BBCH 65) and gradually declined through the later growth stages, reaching the minimum values at full ripe stage of wheat (BBCH 89). SRIs, such as a Normalized pigment chlorophyll ratio index (NPCI), Inversion of the simple ratio (ISR) and Normalized difference water index (NDWI), as well as for individual spectral bands, increased from BBCH 65 stage and showed the greatest values at the end of growing season, Table 2.

Table 2. Mean values for the stem height, spike length and the spectral reflection indices (SRIs) measured for 4 winter wheat genotypes at 3 growth stages in all environments.

Environments	K - 0	10	100	1000	K - 0	10	100	1000	K - 0	10	100	1000
	mg l- 1											
Growth stage												
SVIs	BBCH 65				BBCH 75				BBCH 89			
RED	13.08	10.60	22.91	13.30	29.28	26.81	12.46	32.78	86.90	81.13	71.94	70.52
GREEN	25.02	21.17	41.25	22.05	47.14	48.89	23.41	50.18	114.1	117.0	103.9	84.67
BLUE	15.29	13.09	20.03	10.83	23.86	24.43	13.49	24.53	68.49	74.84	60.40	52.45
INFRARED	102.4	95.57	111.8	82.10	125.1	127.3	106.8	119.7	181.3	180.4	162.0	138.3
NDVI	0.749	0.781	0.901	0.684	0.622	0.641	0.768	0.550	0.367	0.398	0.414	0.339
RDVI	9.182	8.996	9.407	7.934	9.483	9.753	9.389	8.672	9.155	9.567	8.785	7.795
NDVIg	0.583	0.620	0.718	0.560	0.447	0.449	0.615	0.420	0.238	0.259	0.287	0.242
NDVIb	0.740	0.762	0.951	0.767	0.682	0.680	0.772	0.670	0.467	0.450	0.520	0.474
SR	8.949	10.03	6.025	7.077	5.430	5.628	9.552	4.533	2.646	2.665	3.178	2.290
IPVI	0.874	0.890	1.076	0.842	0.811	0.820	0.884	0.775	0.683	0.699	0.707	0.670
GARI	0.619	0.669	0.677	0.484	0.395	0.437	0.628	0.312	0.144	0.210	0.206	0.325
SAVI	1.118	1.165	1.222	1.020	0.929	0.958	1.146	0.822	0.549	0.596	0.619	0.507
GSAVI	0.871	0.926	0.949	0.836	0.669	0.672	0.919	0.626	0.356	0.387	0.429	0.362
GOSAVI	0.583	0.619	0.717	0.559	0.447	0.449	0.614	0.419	0.238	0.258	0.287	0.242
NPCI	- 0.047	- 0.063	0.333	0.134	0.084	0.047	- 0.005	0.171	0.114	0.063	0.126	0.158
GCI	3.444	3.866	2.562	3.105	1.971	2.084	3.995	1.848	0.950	0.873	1.378	0.792

GRVI	0.308	0.325	0.513	0.225	0.254	0.277	0.302	0.184	0.144	0.158	0.146	0.110
NLI	0.996	0.996	1.245	0.993	0.995	0.995	0.996	0.992	0.992	0.994	0.990	0.990
TDVI	1.276	1.308	1.417	1.204	1.130	1.153	1.295	1.032	0.762	0.825	0.835	0.723
WDRVI	0.199	0.268	0.261	0.079	-	-	0.240	-	-	-	-	-
					0.032	0.003		0.133	0.360	0.339	0.305	0.398
GRDVI	0.430	0.480	0.528	0.369	0.246	0.261	0.467	0.186	-	-	0.029	-
									0.029	0.005		0.043
GBNDVI	0.419	0.463	0.557	0.416	0.277	0.277	0.468	0.249	0.019	0.023	0.080	0.018
RBNDVI	0.548	0.590	0.693	0.516	0.410	0.422	0.590	0.348	0.100	0.111	0.159	0.079
PNDVI	0.295	0.347	0.404	0.256	0.118	0.128	0.345	0.065	-	-	-	-
									0.167	0.157	0.108	0.184
ISR	0.148	0.127	0.471	0.196	0.246	0.231	0.136	0.311	0.491	0.449	0.442	0.517
NDWI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.583	0.620	0.218	0.560	0.447	0.449	0.615	0.420	0.238	0.259	0.287	0.242
GLI	0.274	0.280	0.539	0.267	0.282	0.287	0.287	0.245	0.189	0.183	0.192	0.169
WDRVI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.122	0.054	0.057	0.237	0.343	0.318	0.081	0.426	0.607	0.596	0.564	0.639
Plant height	76.08	85.33	87.33	65.17	76.08	85.33	87.08	65.17	76.08	85.33	87.08	65.17
Spike length	10.10	10.75	11.08	9.40	10.11	10.75	10.83	9.40	10.11	10.75	10.83	9.40

*Environment labels represents control (0), 10, 100 and 1000 mg l⁻¹ primed concentrations of ZnO NPs applied.

Regarding to the environmental conditions, within stage of BBCH 65, the greatest values was found in conditions of 100 mg l⁻¹ than at 10 mg l⁻¹NPs ZnO applied, while the lower values of SRIs were found in cultivars in control conditions. Within BBCH 75, the greatest values was found in conditions of 100 mg l⁻¹ and 10 mg l⁻¹NPs ZnO applied, while the lower values of SRIs were found in cultivars in control conditions. Within BBCH 89, the greatest values was found in conditions of 100 mg l⁻¹ and 10 mg l⁻¹NPs ZnO applied, while the lower values of SRIs were found in cultivars in control conditions. The lowest values of SRIs were found in maximum concentration of ZnO NPs within BBCH 65, BBCH 75 and BBCH 89 (Table 2). This results indicated that ZnO NPs increased the plant growth and yield components, such as a stem height and spike length which was reflected through spectral reflectance signature.

Relationship between yield components and spectral reflectance indices.

Highly significant ($P < 0.01$) positive correlations between stem height and spike length of wheat were observed at BBCH 65 ($r = 0.689^{**}$) and BBCH 75 stage of wheat ($r = 0.740^{**}$).

In present study SRIs expressed better sensitivity than individual spectral bands for green vegetation detection and showed better correlation with observed traits under each treatment. With respect to the association between stem height and SRIs, the result revealed that the positive and highly significant association for most of SRIs were observed at the full flowering (BBCH 65) stage of wheat (Table 3). Positive and highly significant correlations were also observed in BBCH 65 between stem height and GSAVI ($r = 0.674^{**}$), NDVIg ($r = 0.672^{**}$), GOSAVI ($r = 0.672^{**}$), GRDVI ($r = 0.661^{**}$), GCI ($r = 0.661^{**}$) and GCI ($r = 0.661^{**}$). Significant and positive correlations were also observed between stem height and GARI ($r = 0.622^*$), PNDVI ($r = 0.605^*$), NDVI ($r = 0.600^*$), IPVI ($r = 0.600^*$), SAVI ($r = 0.600^*$), WDRVI ($r = 0.596^*$), TDVI ($r = 0.593^*$), NPCI ($r = 0.527^*$), NLI ($r = 0.524^*$), RBNDVI ($r = 0.517^*$), SR ($r = 0.515^*$), GBNDVI ($r = 0.514^*$). Positive, but not significant correlations were observed between stem height and RDVI ($r = 0.414$), GRVI ($r = 0.415$), VARI ($r = 0.387$) and GLI ($r = 0.121$). Single band which had higher positive correlations were INFRARED ($r = 0.353$) and BLUE ($r = 0.246$). During the medium milk stage of wheat (BBCH 75), the largest positive and significant relation were observed between stem height and TDVI ($r = 0.522^*$), while the weaker and non significant relationships was observed in the full ripe stage of wheat. Highly significant negative correlations between stem height of wheat and the SRIs at BBCH 65 were observed for NDWI ($r = -0.672^{**}$). Significant negative correlation was also found for ISR ($r = -0.593^*$), SIPI ($r = -0.562^*$) while negative and non significant relation was observed for PSRI ($r = -0.182$) and TGI ($r = -0.014$). At BBCH 75, significant negative correlation were found for ISR and SIPI and non-significant for PSRI ($r = -0.391$), MSR ($r = -0.383$) and TGI ($r = -0.037$), Table 3.

With regard to the trait of the spike length, the greatest positive and highly significant correlations between spike length and SRIs were found at medium milk stage of wheat (BBCH 75). In BBCH 75 the largest correlation were observed TDVI ($r = 0.798^{**}$), NDVI ($r = 0.781^{**}$), IPVI ($r = 0.781^{**}$), SAVI ($r = 0.781^{**}$), WDRVI ($r = 0.745^{**}$), RBNDVI ($r = 0.728^{**}$), SR ($r = 0.671^{**}$), GRVI ($r = 0.663^{**}$). Significant positive association was found for GARI, GDVI, PNDVI, NLI with r values of up to 0.629^* . At BBCH 75, between spike length of wheat and the vegetation indices highly significant negative correlations was found for ISR ($r = -0.798^{**}$), SIPI ($r = -0.693^{**}$) and negative and nonsignificant for NDWI ($r = -0.422$), PSRI ($r = -0.464$) and MSR ($r = -0.587$). At BBCH 65 significant positive correlations were observed between stem height and NDVIg ($r = 0.732^{**}$), GOSAVI ($r = 0.730^{**}$), GSAVI ($r = 0.725^{**}$), PNDVI ($r = 0.713^{**}$), GBNDVI ($r = 0.712^{**}$), GRDVI ($r = 0.685^{**}$), RBNDVI ($r = 0.662^{**}$). Significant positive association was found for NDVI ($r = 0.600^*$), IPVI ($r = 0.600^*$), WDRVI ($r = 0.600^*$), TDVI ($r = 0.593^*$), SAVI ($r = 0.593^*$), SR ($r = 0.574^*$). At BBCH 65, between spike length of wheat and the SRIs significant negative and highly significant correlations were observed for NDWI ($r = -0.732^{**}$) and MSR ($r = -0.730^{**}$). Significant negative was found for single RED ($r = -0.609^*$) and ISR ($r = -0.595^*$). Negative and nonsignificant correlation were found for SIPI ($r = -0.382$), NPCI ($r = -0.361$), TGI ($r = -0.359$) and PSRI ($r = -0.182$), Table 3.

Table 3. Pearson's correlations coefficients between stem height (cm), spike length (cm) and evaluated spectral SRIs of 4 winter wheat genotypes measured at 3 growth stages.

SVIs	Stem height (cm)			Spike length (cm)		
	BBCH 65	BBCH 75	BBCH 89	BBCH 65	BBCH 75	BBCH 89
RED	-0.122	-0.319	0.028	-0.609 *	-0.498	0.086
GREEN	0.079	-0.141	0.151	-0.366	-0.165	0.110
BLUE	0.246	-0.135	0.153	-0.231	-0.264	0.103
INFRARED	0.353	-0.001	0.200	-0.057	0.061	0.224
NDVI	0.600*	0.503	0.343	0.600*	0.781**	0.344
NDVIg	0.672**	0.229	0.127	0.732**	0.422	0.365
NDVIb	0.060	0.188	0.067	0.412	0.441	0.302
SR	0.515*	0.361	0.402	0.574*	0.671**	0.233
IPVI	0.600*	0.503	0.343	0.600*	0.781**	0.344
GARI	0.622*	0.423	-0.112	0.480	0.609*	-0.328
SAVI	0.600*	0.504	0.344	0.593*	0.781**	0.345
GSAVI	0.674**	0.232	0.127	0.725**	0.424	0.365
GOSAVI	0.672**	0.230	0.127	0.730**	0.422	0.365
NPCI	0.527*	-0.327	-0.426	-0.361	-0.474	0.008
GCI	0.661**	0.260	0.267	0.457	0.446	0.347
GRVI	0.415	0.447	0.327	0.450	0.663**	-0.147
NLI	0.524*	0.410	0.145	0.374	0.515*	0.291
TDVI	0.593*	0.522*	0.325	0.593*	0.798**	0.375
WDRVI	0.596*	0.465	0.374	0.600*	0.745**	0.289
GRDVI	0.662**	0.385	0.233	0.685**	0.629*	0.374
GBNDVI	0.514*	0.230	0.135	0.712**	0.440	0.366
RBNDVI	0.517*	0.439	0.251	0.662**	0.728**	0.375
PNDVI	0.605*	0.362	0.222	0.713**	0.607*	0.385
ISR	-0.593*	-0.521*	-0.324	-0.595*	-0.798**	-0.374
NDWI	-0.672**	-0.229	-0.127	-0.732**	-0.422	-0.365
GLI	0.121	0.444	0.211	0.398	0.663**	-0.090
WDRVI	0.584*	0.440	0.386	0.596*	0.726**	0.265

Stem height	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.689**	0.740**	0.689**
Spike length	0.689**	0.740**	0.689**	1.000	1.000	1.000

*– Significant at $P < 0.05$ probability level, ** – Highly significant at $P < 0.01$ probability level.

Between stem height of wheat and SRIs significant positive correlations were observed mostly at full flowering stage. Among the number of different SRIs, which are based on a combination of visible and NIR wavelengths, NDVIg (Green Normalised Difference Vegetation Index) on average, performed better than the others and was relatively consistent in all stages for both traits. NDVIg is index which indicates canopy photosynthetic area and exactly it is a modified version of NDVI, which substitutes the green band in place of the red band in the NDVI equation. The GNDVI is sensitive to the chlorophyll concentration in vegetation, when the leaf area index is moderately high. Hence, NDVIg overcomes the problems with saturation, which NDVI exhibits for some vegetation types at later growth stages because it is more sensitive to low chlorophyll concentrations (Gitelson et al., 1996; Mashaba et al., 2016). Consistent and higher correlation between NDVIg and grain yield traits of wheat has been also reported by Babar et al. (2007).

With a few exceptions, between spike length of wheat and SRIs significant positive correlations were observed mostly at BBCH 75 stage of wheat. According to Apparacio et al. (2000) the weaker relationships recorded between the SRIs and spike length during BBCH 65 compared with those for stem height, might have been the result of the difficulties encountered in measuring properly the green area of spike. According to the Shibayama et al. (1986) the relationship between SRIs and canopy parameters has been reported as being disturbed by the presence of the spike. Within BBCH 75 the greatest relation was observed between TDVI which was expected, since that TDVI does not saturate like NDVI and SAVI. Also the greatest positive correlation between spike length and NDVI in BBCH 75 was observed, as a consequence of lower amounts of green biomass. It may be explained as during the crop cycle, after flowering, vegetation shows a decrease in reflectance in the near-infrared bands, an increased red reflectance in the chlorophyll active band. According to Apparacio et al. (2000) ontogenetic changes in the spectral signature lead to a decrease in either NDVI and SR. Similarly to the present findings, the highest correlation with wheat grain yield was obtained with the NDVI and at the grain filling start stage was reported by Wang et al. (2014). Negative correlation between NDWI and both traits may be expected since that the NDWI (Normalised Difference Water Index) is a moisture index for determining vegetation water content and mainly indicated as an effective tool for water stress, soil, vegetation moisture conditions and water content in vegetative areas, which was determined by the NIR (Tuvdendorj et al., 2019). According to McFeeters (1996) the NDWI is designed to enhance the reflectance of water by using the green wavelengths, decreasing the low reflectance of NIR by water features and taking into account that vegetation and soil features have a high reflectance of NIR.

In general, except few exceptions, all SRIs had positive correlations with the measured parameters under each treatment. However, these indicate that it is possible to deal with different SRIs as indirect selection traits like the traditional grain yield related traits.

CONCLUSION

Despite the fact that each environment has its own characteristics and influence on plant response the overall results showed that statistically significant correlations were predominantly influenced by the phenological stage of estimation and the index used. This investigation indicated that by combining spectral reflectance data with an appropriate statistical analysis during different grown stages, it is possible to accurately assess the growth and yield components of winter wheat genotypes. The comparison of many indices could also serve for recommending specific indices and can contribute to the optimization of sensors, the selection of measurement dates and specific SRIs.

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REFERENCES:

- Aparicio, N., Villegas, D., Casadesus, J., Araus, J.L., Royo, C. (2000): Spectral Vegetation Indices as Nondestructive Tools for Determining Durum Wheat Yield. *Agron. J.* 92: 83–91.
- Araus, J.L., Casadesus, J., Bort, J. (2001): Recent tools for the screening of physiological traits determining yield. In 'Application of physiology in wheat breeding'. (Eds MP Reynolds, JI Ortiz-Monasterio, A McNab), 59–77. (CIMMYT: Mexico).
- Babar, M.A., Reynolds, M.P., Van Ginkel, M., Klatt, A.R., Raun, W.R., Stone, M.L. (2006a): Spectral reflectance indices as a potential indirect selection criteria for wheat yield under irrigation. *Crop Science* 46, 578–588. doi: 10.2135/cropsci2005.0059
- Babar, M.A., Ginkel, M., Reynolds, M.P., Prasad, B. and Klatt, A.R. (2007): Heritability, correlated response, and indirect selection involving spectral reflectance indices and grain yield in wheat. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 58, 432–442.
- Bannari, A., Morin, D., Bonn, F., Huete, A.R. (1995): A review of vegetation indices. *Remote Sens Rev.* 13 (1–2): 95–120.
- Bolton, D. K., Friedl, M. A. (2013). Forecasting crop yield using remotely sensed vegetation indices and crop phenology metrics. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 173, 1, 74-84.
- El-Hendawy, S., Al-Suhaibani, N., Dewir, Y.H., Elsayed, S., Alotaibi, M., Hassan, W., Refay, Y., Tahir, M.U. (2019): Ability of modified spectral reflectance indices for estimating growth and photosynthetic efficiency of wheat under saline field conditions. *Agronomy*, 9 (1):35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy9010035>.
- Evans, L.T. and Fisher, R.A. (1999): Yield potential its definition, measurement, and significance. *Crop Science*, 39, 6, 1544–1551.
- Gitelson, A.A, Kaufman, Y.J., Merzlyak, M.N. (1996): Use of green channel in remote sensing of global vegetation from EOS-MODIS', *Remote Sensing of the Environment*, 58, 3, 289-298.
- Gutierrez, M., Reynolds, M.P., Raun, W.R., Stone, M.L., Klatt, A.R. (2010): Spectral water indices for assessing yield in elite bread wheat genotypes under well-irrigated, water-stressed, and high-temperature conditions. *Crop Sci.* 50, 197–214.

Index database for remote sensing indices (<https://www.indexdatabase.de/info/idb.php>).

Kraljević-Balalić, M., Dimitrijević, M., Petrović, S. (1995): Interakcija genotip/sredina za komponente prinosa. I simpozijum oplemenjivanja organizama. Vrnjačka Banja, 58.

Kitić, G., Tagarakis, A., Cselyuszka, N., Panić, M., Birgermajer, S., D. Sakulski, D., Matović, J. (2019): A new low-cost portable multispectral optical device for precise plant status assessment. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 162, 300-308.

Khan, Z., Rahimi-Eichi, V., Haefele, S. (2018): Estimation of vegetation indices for high-throughput phenotyping of wheat using aerial imaging. *Plant Methods* 14, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13007-018-0287-6>.

Ljubičić, N., Radović, M., Kostić, M., Popović, V., Radulović, M., Blagojević, D., Ivošević, B. (2020): The impact of ZnO nanoparticles application on yield components of different wheat genotypes. *Agriculture and Forestry*, 66 (2): 217-227. DOI:10.17707/AgricultForest.66.2.19.

Mashaba, Z., Chirima, G., Botai, J., Combrinck, L., Munghemezulu, C. (2016): Evaluating Spectral Indices for Winter Wheat Health Status Monitoring in Bloemfontein using Lsat 8 data. *South African Journal of Geomatics*, Vol. 5. No. 2, September 2016, 227-243.

McFeeters, S.K. (1995): The use of normalized difference water index (NDWI) in the delineation of open water features, *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 17, 7, 1425-1432.

Munir, T., Rizwan, M., Kashif, M., Shahzad, A., Ali, S. (2018): Effect of zinc oxide nanoparticles on the growth and Zn uptake in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) by seed priming method. *Digest Journal of Nanomaterials and Biostructures*, 13 (1): 315-323.

Petrović, S., M. Dimitrijević, N. Ljubičić and B. Banjac. (2012): Diallel analysis of quantitative traits in wheat crosses. In: *Proceedings of the 47th Croatian and 7th International Symposium on Agriculture*, Publisher University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Croatia, pp. 313-317.

Prasad, B., Carver, B.F., Stone, M.L., Babar, M. A., Raun, W. R., Klatt, A. R. (2007): Potential use of spectral reflectance indices as a selection tool for grain yield in winter wheat under great plains conditions. *Crop Sci.*, 47, 1426–1440.

Reynolds, M. P. and H. J. Braun (2013): Achieving yield gains in wheat: Overview. In: *Proceedings of the 3th International Workshop of the Wheat Yield Consortium*, CENEB, CIMMYT, Cd. Obregon, Sonora, Mexico, D. F., CIMMYT.

Royo, C., Aparicio, N., Villegas, D., Casadesus, J., Monneveux, P, Araus. J.L. (2003): Usefulness of spectral reflectance indices as durum wheat yield predictors under contrasting Mediterranean conditions. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 24, 4403–4419. doi: 10.1080/0143116031000150059.

Rizwan, M., Ali S., Ali B., Adrees M., Arshad M., Hussain A., Zia ur Rehman M., Waris A.A. (2019): Zinc and iron oxide nanoparticles improved the plant growth and reduced the oxidative stress and cadmium concentration in wheat, *Chemosphere*, 214, 269-277.

STATISTICA (Data Analysis Software System), version 13. Tulsa, OK, 2017 (www.statsoft.com).

Shibayama, M., C.L. Wiegand, and A.J. Richardson. (1986): Diurna patterns of bidirectional vegetation indices for wheat canopies. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 7:233–246.

Tuvdendorj, B., Wu, H., Zeng, G. Batdelger, L. Nanzad, L. (2019): Determination of appropriate remote sensing indices for spring wheat yield estimation in Mongolia. *Remote Sensing*, 11, 2568.

L. Wang, Y. Tian, X. Yao, Y. Zhu, W. Cao (2014): Predicting grain yield and protein content in wheat by fusing multi-sensor and multi-temporal remote-sensing images. *Field Crops Res.*, 164, 178-188.

Zečević, V., Knežević, D., Mićanović, D. and Madić, M. (2008): Genetic and phenotypic variability of spike length and plant height in wheat. *Kragujevac J. Sci.*, 30, 125-130.